

Studies in Acetyl Bromide as a Polar Solvent. Part IV. Conductometric Titrations in Acetyl Bromide

Ram Chand Paul, Jit Kaur, and Sarjit Singh Sandhu.

Existence of solvo-acids, solvo-bases, and ansolvo-bases in acetyl bromide, as already postulated, has been confirmed conductometrically in solutions. Stannic bromide and antimony tribromide have been used as solvo-acids. Solutions of α -picoline, quinoline, isoquinoline, and dimethylaniline have been used as solvo-bases and the quaternary ammonium halides, viz., tetraethylammonium bromide, triethylbenzylammonium bromide, dimethylethylphenylammonium bromide, and dimethylphenylbenzylammonium bromide, have been used as ansolvo-bases. The breaks in curves corresponding to different acid/base molar ratios have been noted, indicating the formation of acid or normal salts. Most of the complexes isolated in Part III have been confirmed and the formation of numerous others has been indicated. The formation of these complexes is explained on the basis of the existence of ionic species in the solutions of acetyl bromide.

In Part I of the series (*this issue*, p. 81) formation of the solvates of the Lewis acids and bases in acetyl bromide has been discussed and based on the conductance of their solutions, the ionisation of solvo-acids, solvo-, and ansolvo-bases has been indicated. The formation of acid/base neutralisation complexes, which have been isolated and analysed, has been presented in Part III of the series (*this issue*, p. 89). Recently conductometric titrations have gained considerable importance in the study of acid-base neutralisation reactions in polar solvents (Smith, *Chem. Rev.*, 1938, **23**, 165; Gutman, *Monatsh.*, 1954, **85**, 404; *Z. anorg.allgem.Chem.*, 1951, **266**, 331; Manhas *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 325; Paul *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1960, **37**, 195). In the present work the acid-base neutralisation reactions have been studied conductometrically and the existence of complexes mentioned in Part III has been confirmed and that of quite a few new complexes has been indicated.

Addition of a solution of stannic bromide to that of tetraethylammonium bromide in acetyl bromide results in the formation of a yellow precipitate accompanied by a decrease in the conductance of the solution until it reaches a minimum at an acid/base molar ratio of 1:2 (Fig. 1) at which the precipitation is complete. On further addition of the acid solution, the precipitate begins to dissolve and the conductance shows a sharp increase. A second break appears at acid/base molar ratio of 1:1. Here the dissolution of the precipitate is complete. Further addition of the acid brings about only a slight increase in the conductance, as is clear from the third portion of the curve (Fig. 1).

The changes in the value of conductance of the solution of tetraethylammonium bromide in acetyl bromide, with the addition of stannic bromide solution, may be interpreted in terms of the existence of ionic species in solution (Parts I and II, *this issue*, pp. 81, 85).

Tetraethylammonium bromide increases the conductance of acetyl bromide solution due to its ionisation as :

where Q stands for a quaternary ammonium radical. Since it increases the concentration of Br^{-} ions (anions specific of the solvent) it acts as an ansolvo-base. Addition of stannic bromide

to acetyl bromide also increases the conductance (Part I, *loc. cit.*), which may be explained on the basis of the formation of a solvo-acid in solution.

Addition of the acidic solution to the basic solution results in the precipitation of the normal complex, bis-tetraethylammonium hexabromostannate. This results in the progressive removal of tetraethylammonium and bromide ions from solution with consequent decrease in conductance.

The first break indicates the completion of this reaction. On further addition of the stannic bromide solution the precipitate of the normal complex begins to dissolve to form tetramethylammonium acetylhexabromostannate as follows :

The acid salt, QAcSnBr_6 , is more strongly ionised in solution than Q_2SnCl_6 or Ac_2SnCl_6 . Its progressive formation results in an enormous increase in conductance of the solution. Once dissolution is complete, the conductance is only slightly affected by any further addition of the acid solution, which itself is comparatively feebly ionised.

FIG. 1

The results of the titration of antimony tribromide with tetraethylammonium bromide are also represented in Fig. 1. The addition of antimony tribromide solution to that of tetraethylammonium bromide in acetyl bromide results in the formation of a precipitate and in an enormous decrease in conductance of the reaction mixture. This decrease continues to the point of minimum conductance where the acid/base molar ratio is 1:2 and the precipitation of the complex is complete. On further addition of the acid solution the precipitate begins to dissolve with a corresponding rise in conductance of the solution. At acid/base molar ratio of 1:1, the precipitate

is completely dissolved and there is a break in the curve. Further on, the rate of increase of conductance is much lower. There is a third break, which records maximum conductance at acid/base molar ratio of 3:2. After this the conductance again begins to decrease; possibly there is a fourth break at the acid/base molar ratio of 2:1. After this stage the conductance of the solution remains almost constant in spite of further additions of the acid solution.

Antimony tribromide is capable of acting as a monobasic acid and a tribasic acid where antimony is tetravalent and hexavalent. Formation of these four complexes can be explained on the basis of the hexacovalency of antimony:

The acid $(\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_3\text{SbBr}_6$ can act as mono or dibasic acid depending on if one or two of the CH_3CO groups ionise:

Formation of the precipitate with the acid/base molar ratio of 1:2 may be represented as:

A complex of this type has been isolated with tetramethylammonium bromide in acetyl bromide (Part III, *loc. cit.*), which supports the formation of hexavalent antimony. Further addition of the acid solution leads to the formation of 1:1 complex, $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N} \cdot (\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_2\text{SbBr}_6$, which has been isolated in its desolvated form $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N} \cdot \text{SbBr}_6$ (Part III).

In Fig. 2 the results of the conductometric titration of triethylbenzylammonium bromide with stannic bromide are presented. The curve shows the formation of the normal complex $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_7\text{H}_7]_2 \cdot \text{SnBr}_6$ and the acid complex $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_7\text{H}_7 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{CO} \cdot \text{SnBr}_6$ corresponding to the breaks in the curve at acid/base molar ratio of 1:2 and 1:1 respectively. Formation of these complexes and their conductometric behaviour can be explained on the lines similar to those recorded for the titration of tetraethylammonium bromide against stannic bromide.

In Fig. 3 are shown the results of the titration of the solvo-acids, stannic bromide and antimony tribromide, against the ansolvo-base, dimethylphenylammonium bromide. The titration of stannic bromide against the quaternary ammonium bromide is exactly similar to its titration against tetraethylammonium bromide and shows formation of the normal complex with acid/base molar ratio of 1:2 and the acid salt with the acid/base molar ratio of 1:1.

Titration of antimony tribromide here is slightly different from the one with tetraethylammonium bromide. In the present case antimony tribromide acts as a monobasic acid, *i.e.*, the covalency of antimony is restricted to four.

FIG. 3

The conductance of the ansolvo-base decreases regularly with addition of the acid solution and a simultaneous separation of the normal complex, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}\cdot\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\cdot\text{SbBr}_4$, till the first break at the acid/base molar ratio of 1:1 is reached. On further addition of the acid solution there is practically very little effect on the conductance of the solution since the acid solution is comparatively feebly ionised. The normal complex does not dissolve. These changes can be represented as :

FIG. 4

In Fig. 4 are shown the conductometric titration curves of the titrations of the ansolvo-base, dimethylphenylbenzylammonium bromide, against the solvo-acids, stannic bromide and antimony tribromide. The curves obtained are very similar to those obtained in the case of dimethyl-ethylphenylammonium bromide, as depicted in Fig 3, and can be explained exactly on similar lines.

FIG. 5

α -Picoline, which has already been used as a solvo-base in acetyl chloride (Manhas *et al.*, *loc. cit.*), has been employed in the study of conductometric titrations with stannic bromide and antimony tribromide in acetyl bromide. The results obtained are plotted in Fig 5.

α -Picoline dissolves in acetyl bromide and gives a conducting solution (Part I, *loc. cit.*). This analogy with other tertiary bases can be explained on the basis of the formation of the solvate acetyl- α -picolinium bromide and its ionisation.

Addition of stannic bromide solution to that of α -picoline in acetyl bromide lowers the conductance of the latter with formation of a precipitate till a point of minimum conductance is reached at an acid/base molar ratio of 1:2 (Fig. 5).

Any further addition of the stannic bromide solution increases the conductance, but, as expected, there is no second break; the precipitate formed does not dissolve in an excess of the acid solution. This leads to the conclusion that the acid salt formed is comparatively insoluble. The increase in conductance can be due to the formation and ionisation of the acid complex, $(C_9H_7N.CH_3CO)CH_3CO.SnBr_6$, which has some solubility. The existence of the normal complex, $(C_9H_7N.CH_3CO)_2SnBr_6$ has been proved by its isolation and chemical analysis (Part III).

FIG. 6

The titration of α -picoline with antimony tribromide in acetyl bromide indicates only one break representing formation of the complex $(C_9H_7N.CH_3CO)SbBr_4$, existence of which has been proved in Part III (*loc. cit.*).

At acid-base molar ratio of 1:1 formation of the complex is complete and any further addition of the acid does not dissolve the precipitate. Further additions of the acid solution affect the conductance only slightly due to the feeble ionisation of the solvo-acid.

Results of the titrations of stannic bromide and antimony tribromide with quinoline are shown in Fig. 6. This shows the formation of the normal complexes $(C_9H_7N.CH_3CO)_2SnBr_6$ and $(C_9H_7N.CH_3CO)SbBr_4$. The formation of these complexes can be explained on similar lines as in the case of α -picoline. $(C_9H_7N.CH_3CO)SbBr_4$ has been isolated and analysed.

Results of the conductometric titrations of isoquinoline with stannic bromide and antimony tribromide in acetyl bromide are plotted in Fig. 7. Titrations with stannic bromide indicate

formation of only the normal complex, $(C_9H_7N.CH_3CO)_2SnBr_6$, *i.e.*, with acid/base molar ratio of 1:2. This complex also does not completely dissolve in an excess of the acid solution.

FIG. 7

The titration of isoquinoline with antimony tribromide shows the formation of 1:1 compound (Fig. 7). The course of conductometric titration and the formation of complexes can be explained on similar lines as in the case of α -picoline.

Dimethylaniline has also been used as a base in acetyl bromide. Its titration with antimony

FIG. 8

tribromide is represented in Fig. 8. On addition of antimony tribromide solution to that of dimethylaniline in acetyl bromide, there is an increase in conductance till the acid/base molar ratio of 1:2 is reached, where there is a break in the curve. There is another break at the ratio of 1:1, beyond which the curve is again more steep. It has been noted for the first time in the present series that throughout the course of titration, an insoluble complex is not formed. This is a big difference as compared with the earlier titrations in all of which insoluble normal salt is formed resulting in a decrease of conductance. Here a change of species is represented by a change of the slope of the curve. The course of this curve can be explained by taking into

account hexacovalency of trivalent antimony :

EXPERIMENTAL

The solvent and the Lewis acids and bases were purified as already described (Part I, *loc. cit.*). For the present work acetyl bromide, purified as above, was again distilled through a special fractionating column and collected at a take-off ratio of 1:5.

A glass conductivity cell equipped with a microburette, replaceable platinum electrodes, and a calcium chloride guard tube was employed. The solutions were kept at a constant temperature by circulating water in the jacket of the cell from a thermostat maintained at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. Stirring of the solution was done with the help of a magnetic stirrer. Resistance of the solutions was measured by using a precision measuring bridge of type WBR No. 108 with logarithmic indicator amplifier type TAV.IKC, No. 034 (Wissenschaftlich-Technische Werkstätten, Weilheim/oby., Germany).

In Figs. 1-8 the molar ratio of acid/base has been plotted against the relative conductance, which is equal to $1/R$. The cell constant has not been taken into account due to the difficulty of placing the electrodes in exactly the same position in the cell. During the course of each titration the electrodes were, however, kept fixed.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY,
CHANDIGARH-3.

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